

Studies on the Changes in Interaction Energies of Salicylic Acid and Salicylate Ion from the Solubility and Dissociation Constant Measurements of the Acid in Ethanol+Water Mixtures

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Manuscript received 27 March 1992, revised 21 July 1992, accepted 10 August 1992

Solubilities of salicylic acid in ethanol+water (0–87.6 wt%) mixtures have been determined. The Gibbs energy changes of transfer of salicylic acid from aqueous to aquo ethanolic solvents have been coupled with the Gibbs energy changes of transfer for the dissociation process to determine the Gibbs energy changes of transfer for salicylate ion. The results are interpreted in terms of ion-solvent interactions and structural variations of the solvent mixtures. Attempts have been made to calculate the interaction energies of benzoic acid and benzoate ion, salicylic acid and salicylate ion utilising the scaled particle theory and the data obtained in the present work and the previous works. The Gibbs energy changes of transfer due to interaction i.e. $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ (water→organic solvents) are negative and favourable in case of salicylic acid and benzoic acid but $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ due to OH group is increasingly positive indicating that OH group in the *ortho*-position of benzoic acid hinders dissolution process.

The $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ (Bz) and $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ (HSal⁻) are positive and $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ (Bz⁻) > $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ (HSal⁻). The $\Delta G_{i(in)}^{\circ}$ due to OH group is seen to be increasingly favourable in qualitative agreement with the fact that the salicylate anion is stabilised due to hydrogen bonding leading to an increased dissociation of salicylic acid. The limitations of the method have also been discussed.

Salicylic acid and its derivatives are well known for their analytic and pharmacologic activities. The presence of OH group in the *ortho*-position of benzoic acid brings about a marked change in its physicochemical and drug activities¹⁻³.

As part of our programme of systematic investigation on the ion-solvent (or solute-solvent) interactions of organic molecules of biological and medicinal interest, we have determined the solubility (analytically and spectrophotometrically) and the dissociation constants (pH-metrically and conductometrically) of salicylic acid in ethanol+water mixtures. The results are presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for the reaction,

where H_2Sal = salicylic acid, is given by

$$K_a = \frac{C_{H^+} C_{HSal^-}}{C_{H_2Sal}} \cdot \frac{f^{\pm}}{f_{H_2Sal}} = \frac{C_{H^+}}{(C_T - C_{H^+})} \cdot \frac{f_{\pm}^{\pm}}{f_{H_2Sal}} \quad (2)$$

where, C_T is the total concentration of salicylic acid and C_{H^+} the concentration of H^+ ion in the saturated solutions of salicylic acid in aqueous and mixed

solvents which were determined pH-metrically as described in the literature⁴⁻⁷. The activity coefficients of the ions were calculated using Davies equation⁸,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = \frac{AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.2\mu \quad (3)$$

with appropriate A -values in each solvent mixture. The activity coefficients of neutral salicylic acid were assumed to be unity in the saturated solutions of the acid in the respective solvents.

The H^+ ion concentration in mixed solvents gradually increases but decreases at 87.6 wt% of ethanol (Table 1). The results are consistent with the fact that though the degree of dissociation decreases but the solubility of the acid increases appreciably leading to an increase in H^+ ion concentration with the alcohol concentration. However, at very high percentages of alcohol (i.e. at 87 wt%), the solubility is large so that increased association rather than dissociation of salicylic acid occurs leading to a decrease in H^+ ion concentration.

The accuracy of the pK-values of the acid determined pH-metrically and the solubility (Table 1) is limited as the solubility of H_2Sal increases appreciably at high percentages of alcohol which may cause f_{H_2Sal} to change appreciably from unity.

TABLE 1 - SOLUBILITY AND pK VALUES OF SALICYLIC ACID IN ETHANOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Ethanol wt%	Solubility CT mol dm ⁻³	Corrected pH	A-values	pK _a
0.0	0.015 8	2.46	0.509	3.00
8.0	0.022 1	2.40	0.555	3.13
16.4	0.035 2	2.43	0.613	3.44
25.3	0.079 0	2.37	0.694	3.70
34.4	0.249	2.21	0.791	3.92
44.0	0.809	2.08	0.927	4.11
54.1	0.985	1.96	1.133	4.17
64.7	1.415	1.87	1.348	4.20
76.0	1.740	1.82	1.707	4.30
87.6	1.945	2.08	2.179	4.84

Moreover, at high percentages, measurement of H⁺ ion concentration in presence of excess of electrolytes is less reliable.

In view of the limitations, accurate values of the dissociation constants of salicylic acid were determined conductometrically using the method of computation suggested by Fuoss-Kraus^{9,10},

$$\frac{F(Z)}{\Delta} = \frac{1}{K\Delta_0^2} \frac{cf_z^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{\Delta_0} \quad (4)$$

The Δ⁰-values of H₂Sal in the ethanol+water mixtures were obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta_{H_2Sal}^0 = \Delta_{HClO_4}^0 + \Delta_{KHSal}^0 - \Delta_{KClO_4}^0 \quad (5)$$

The Δ-values of HClO₄, KHSal and KClO₄ were plotted against C^{1/2} and extrapolated to infinite dilution to get Δ⁰-values. The plots were found to be linear in water as well as in mixed solvents. The results are given in Table 2. The precision in the pK values of salicylic acid is ± 0.01 unit in water to ± 0.03 units at higher percentages of alcohol. The conductance measurements were made using dilute solutions with proper corrections for the activity coefficients of ions. Under these conditions, f_{H₂Sal} can be reasonably considered to be unity.

The Gibbs energy changes of transfer for the dissociation of salicylic acid have been calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta G_t^0(l) = 2.303RT [\log K(s) - \log K(w)] \quad (6)$$

The Gibbs energy changes of transfer of neutral salicylic acid are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0(H_2Sal) &= -2.303RT \log \frac{C_s}{C_w} \cdot \frac{f_s(H_2Sal)}{f_w(H_2Sal)} \\ &\approx -2.303RT \log C_s/C_w \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where C_s and C_w are molar solubilities of the saturated solutions of the salicylic acid in the solvent (s) and water (w) respectively after appropriate corrections for the dissociation of salicylic acid. The activity coefficients of neutral H₂Sal have been considered to be unity when the activity coefficients refer to the standard states in the respective solvents. The appropriate corrections have been made for the dissociation of salicylic acid in aqueous and mixed solvents.

It is evident from Table 2 that the Δ⁰-values decrease markedly with increasing addition of organic co-solvent^{11,12}. The solubilities of salicylic acid are always lower than those of benzoic acid due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding in salicylic acid.

As expected, the pK_a value of salicylic acid increases continuously with increase in organic co-solvent and shows a linear relationship when plotted against mole fraction and 1/ε well upto ~ 60 wt%, beyond which deviation occurs. It is natural to assume that the solute-solvent interactions are responsible for the deviations.

Division of the Gibbs energy changes of transfer (ΔG_t⁰) into electrostatic [ΔG_{t(e)}⁰] and non-electrostatic [ΔG_{t(non-e)}⁰] contribution, i.e.

$$\Delta G_t^0(l) = \Delta G_{t(e)}^0 + \Delta G_{t(non-e)}^0 \quad (8)$$

has been made in the way suggested by Bates and Robinson¹³ (Table 3) using r_{H⁺} = 0.086 nm^{14,15} and r_{KSal⁻} = 0.275¹¹. The results (-ΔG_{t(non-e)}⁰) suggest increasing basicity of the solvent mixtures. But in view of possible uncertainty in the radii values particularly of r_{H⁺} and r_{HSal⁻}, no positive conclusion should be derived. We, therefore, attempted to analyse the results in terms of single ion Gibbs energy changes of transfer which gives the quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions. Thus from

TABLE 2 - EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES OF ELECTROLYTE AND DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS (pK_a) OF SALICYLIC ACID IN ETHANOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Ethanol wt%	1/ε × 10 ₃	Mole-fraction of ethanol	Λ ₀ (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² equiv. ⁻¹)				pK _a
			HClO ₄	C ₂ H ₅ (OH)OOC	KClO ₄	C ₂ H ₅ (OH)COOH	
0.0	1.27	0.000	416.6	105.4	140.4	381.6	3.00
8.0	1.35	0.033	372.0	94.0	116.9	349.1	3.12
16.4	1.42	0.072	301.5	81.5	95.0	288.0	3.23
25.3	1.53	0.117	250.0	65.3	78.5	236.8	3.41
34.4	1.71	0.171	196.0	55.0	66.0	185.0	3.53
44.0	1.90	0.236	172.6	44.2	58.2	158.6	3.77
54.1	2.14	0.316	142.0	41.5	52.0	131.5	4.02
64.7	2.44	0.419	118.0	38.7	49.5	107.2	4.30
76.0	2.87	0.553	108.0	37.0	48.6	90.4	4.61
87.6	3.37	0.734	92.0	39.8	48.0	83.4	5.07

equation (1), we can write,

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{Sal}) \quad (9)$$

or,

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{Sal}) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) \quad (10)$$

$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{Sal})$, calculated from the solubility values, measures the change in solute solvent interactions in going from water to mixed solvents. $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values have been taken from the earlier works¹⁶. The accuracy of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-)$ values (Table 3) depends on the accuracy of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values. The selection $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values is arbitrary and needs examination and explanation. It is to be noted that the 'single ion' values can only be obtained using 'extrathermodynamic' assumptions with inherent limitations and the values can never be absolute. Moreover, the error ranges can not be precisely calculated. $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values in ethanol+water mixtures over the whole composition ranges have been reported earlier^{17,18}. The method of Bhattacharyya *et al.*¹⁶ is based on the determination of the dissociation constants of the 'isoelectric reaction,

where,

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(11) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{Phen}) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{PhenH}^+) \quad (12)$$

$$\approx \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{PhenH}^+) \quad (13)$$

$$[\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{ion}) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{neut}) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{ion})]$$

The dissociation constants can be determined very accurately in dilute solutions where uncertainties involving ionic strengths, extrapolations can be eliminated. However, the calculation of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{ion})$ using Born equation¹⁹ for unsymmetrical ion (like PhenH⁺) where the charge is not uniformly distributed, may introduce an element of uncertainty. However, our values are in good qualitative agreement with the values reported by Popovych and Dill based on the 'reference electrolyte' tri-isoamyl n-butylammonium tetraphenylborate¹⁷ (TABBPh₄) but differ qualitatively as well as quantitatively from the values reported later using TATB, i.e. tetra-phenylarsonium tetraphenylborate (Ph₄AsBPh₄)¹⁸.

The 'reference electrolyte' method using TATB has been adjudged to be the best method for the determination of single ion values by Kim²⁰, Popovych²¹ and Marcus²².

The single ion values of H⁺ ion are based on the difference in the solubility data of Ph₄AsPi, KBPh₄, KPi, KCl and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{HCl})$ and errors from these determinations are compounded in $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values.

The method is based on the assumption of (i) no ion-pair formation or association (a probability which cannot be ruled out at high percentages of organic solvents), and (ii) micelle formation (highly probable in aqueous solution) and crystal solvate formation.

It is to be noted that the solvation of BPh₄⁻ ion is mainly through dispersion interactions which

increases with the increase in polarisability of the solvent mixtures but the picrate ion is solvated mainly by H-bonding interactions (being greatest in water) as well as dispersion interactions acting in the opposite direction²³. Furthermore the 'reference electrolyte' is composed of large symmetrical counter ions of equal size and solvational properties. The central atom and the charge of such counter ions should be buried by large organic residues to minimise specific interactions with solvent. However, such conditions preclude the formation of ionic compounds and associations may not be ruled out if the saturated solutions of these compounds are not extremely dilute. It is to be noted that tetrahedral solvation of the ions have been assumed by Kim²⁰.

However, the ions are probably not equally solvated in all solvents as TATB cannot be utilised for the determination of single ion conductance values in different solvents²⁴. Therefore, the method can not be taken absolutely free from error. Moreover, the Gibbs energy changes of single ion in acetonitrile determined by Alexander and Parker²⁵ and Popovych *et al.*²⁶ differ considerably though both of them used TATB and both of them used $\log_m \gamma \text{Ph}_4\text{As}^+ = \log_m \gamma \text{BPh}_4^- = -5.81$.

It is thus desirable to use different methods and derive reasonably consistent single ion values. Considering limitations, the results reported by us can be regarded to be fairly good. Moreover, the experimental values (Table 3) of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-)$ are negative and positive respectively, a fact which is observed generally and is also observed in case of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{Bz}^-)$ ^{5,6,20}.

The results indicate that the transfer of H⁺ ion from water to aquo-ethanolic mixture is increasingly favourable with maximum at ~ 65 wt% of ethanol and the transfer of HSa⁻ ion is unfavourable with minimum at ~ 34 wt% of ethanol. These may reflect the characteristic changes in the solvent properties in these regions. It is known that the addition of organic co-solvent first strengthens the three-dimensional polymeric structure of water molecules and becomes minimum in the region mentioned above, thereafter depolymerisation of water molecules takes place with the addition of alcohol. These are reflected in the ultrasonic absorption and the excess properties of mixing²⁷⁻²⁹.

It is expected that the interaction of the solvent molecules with HSa⁻ ion would obviously be less pronounced than that with the neutral H₂Sal due to the more pronounced intramolecular hydrogen bonding possibility in HSa⁻.

In order to have a better idea regarding the ion-solvent interactions, we have calculated the interaction energies of salicylic acid, benzoic acid and their ions using the scaled particle theory (SPT)³⁰. According to this theory,

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ} = \Delta G_{\text{cav}}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{\text{int}}^{\circ} + RT \ln \frac{RT}{V} \quad (14)$$

and

$$\Delta G_S^0(1) = \Delta G_{cav}^0 + \Delta G_{int}^0 + \Delta G_{el}^0 + RT \ln \frac{RT}{V} \quad (15)$$

(For charged species)

where, ΔG_S^0 is the standard Gibbs energy change associated with the dissolution process, ΔG_{cav}^0 the standard Gibbs energy change required to create cavity of suitable size in the solvent to accommodate the solute molecules, ΔG_{int}^0 the standard Gibbs energy change of interaction between solute and solvent, V the molar volume of the solvent and ΔG_{el}^0 the electrostatic Gibbs energy changes. The cavity term can be calculated using equation,

$$\Delta G_{cav}^0 = RT \left\{ -\ln(1-y) + \frac{3y}{i-y} R_1 + \left[\frac{3y}{i-y} + \frac{9}{2} \left(\frac{y}{i-y} \right)^2 \right] R_1^2 + \frac{YP}{kT} R_1^3 \right\} \quad (16)$$

where $y = \pi \rho \sigma_1^3 / 6$ is the reduced density, $R_1 = \sigma_2 / \sigma_1$ the ratio of the hard sphere diameters of the solute (σ_2) and solvent (σ_1), such that the cavity radius is $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) / 2$, P is pressure of the system given by

$$\frac{P}{\rho k T} = \frac{1+y+y^2}{(1-y)^3}$$

and $\rho = N/V$ where ρ is number average density.

It is known that cavity terms calculated using SPT are usually applicable to non-polar solutes. However, in spite of limitations, SPT has been successfully utilised by various workers^{20,31-34} in accounting for the cavity term of polar and ionic solutes in various solvents. Since the theory is based on the properties of the exact radial distribution function which yields approximate expression for the reversible work to introduce a spherical particle into a fluid of spherical particles, the equation should not be strictly applicable to unsymmetrical ions like benzoate or salicylate ion in aqueous or mixed solvents. But in absence of any suitable method, we have utilised the SPT to calculate ΔG_c^0 of ions keeping in mind the limitations of our approach.

We have considered the mixed solvent to be an assorted solvent, and the mean molar mass of the assorted solvent M_s is

$$M_s = 100 / \left\{ \frac{\text{wt\% of organic solvent}}{M_{org. solv.}} + \frac{\text{wt\% of water}}{18.016} \right\} \quad (17)$$

The molar volume of the assorted solvent has been calculated using the relation,

$$V_s = M_s / C_s \quad (18)$$

from which the diameter $\sigma_s (=2r_s) = (6v/N\pi)^{1/3}$ can be obtained. The hard-sphere of the solvent has been obtained using the empirical relationship suggested by Kim²⁰.

$$\sigma_1(\text{SPT}) = (0.9275 \pm 0.0126)\sigma_s - (0.8465 \pm 0.0084) \quad (19)$$

The ΔG_{cav}^0 values in different solvent mixtures have been calculated utilising the data derived from which ΔG_{cav}^0 values can be calculated. The ΔG_{cav}^0 thus calculated are converted into molar scale using the relation,

$$\Delta G_{cav}^0(\text{molar}) = \Delta G_{cav}^0(\text{mole-fraction}) + RT \ln \frac{M_1}{1000\rho_1} \quad (20)$$

The $\Delta G_{cav}^0(\text{molar})$ values at different percentages of organic solvents are recorded in Table 3.

We have also calculated ΔG_{cav}^0 from equation (21) for comparison,

$$\Delta G_{cav}^0 = 4\pi\sigma^2 N \left(1 - \frac{4\delta}{\sigma} \right) \quad (21)$$

where the radius of the cavity in $\sigma = (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) / 2$. The values are given in Table 3. The correction term has been neglected.

Since ΔG_{cav}^0 is not an experimental quantity, proper comparison of the results is not possible. But it is apparent that the values of ΔG_{cav}^0 calculated using SPT and equation (21) differ widely. This is also true for the ΔG_{cav}^0 of Ar in water, calculated using equation (21) (≈ 52.0 kJ) and that calculated by Pierroti (≈ 22.0 kJ). It is possible that the values may come little closer, if we take into consi-

TABLE 3—GIBBS ENERGY CHANGES OF TRANSFER (kJ mol^{-1}) IN ETHANOL+WATER MIXTURE AT 298.15 K

Ethanol wt%	$\Delta G_i^0(1)$	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{nonel})$	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}_2\text{Sal})$	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{H}^+)$	$\Delta G_i^0(\text{HSal}^-)$	$\Delta G^0(\text{cav})$		$\Delta G_i^0(\text{cav})$
						(SPT)	(ST)*	
0.0	—	—	—	—	—	69.38	(92.48)	—
8.0	0.68	-0.17	-0.83	-1.08	0.93	67.99	(64.58)	-1.30
16.4	1.31	-0.28	-1.93	-1.83	1.16	66.88	(53.04)	-2.30
25.3	2.34	-0.42	-3.99	-2.70	1.05	65.81	(46.39)	-3.57
34.4	3.02	-1.64	-6.83	-3.38	-0.43	64.53	(42.33)	-4.84
44.0	4.39	-2.29	-9.04	-4.52	-0.13	62.93	(41.42)	-6.45
54.1	5.82	-3.40	-10.24	-5.53	1.11	61.66	(41.48)	-7.72
64.7	7.41	-4.99	-11.13	-5.63	1.91	59.83	(40.76)	-9.55
76.0	9.18	-7.78	-11.65	-5.53	3.06	57.62	(40.54)	-11.76
87.6	11.81	-10.45	-11.92	-4.66	4.55	55.36	(40.29)	-14.08

*Values calculated from surface tension measurements.

deration the correction term. Lowering of γ -value in presence of electrolytes may be possible but the reason for the large differences can not be explained. We prefer to use the ΔG_{cav}° values obtained using the SPT.

Thus the Gibbs energy changes of transfer of HBz or H_2 Sal from water to mixed solvents can be written as (using equation 11),

$$\Delta G_{t(neut)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M} \quad (22)$$

and

$$\Delta G_{t(neut)}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal}) = G_{t(cav)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal}) + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M} \quad (23)$$

Theoretically, the standard Gibbs energy of solution (ΔG°), by definition, is the change for transferring one mole of solid to the one molar infinite dilution standard state. Thus the cavity term is independent of the magnitude of the actual solubility being dependent only on the radius of the hard-sphere solute (in a particular solvent). However, experimentally, the solubility is determined by the amount of solute dissolved in a solvent at a definite temperature to make a saturated solution in which the chemical potential of the undissolved solute equals that of the dissolved solute and the standard Gibbs energy change is given by $\Delta G^{\circ} = 2.303 RT \log C$, where C represents the solubility, i.e. concentration of solute in the saturated solution (in appropriate units) of the given solvent.

Thus the Gibbs energy changes due to cavity formation should not be the same for HBz and H_2 Sal as the numbers of cavity formed are different due to solubility difference. We, therefore, calculated standard Gibbs energy changes due to cavity formation of neutral HBz or H_2 Sal as

$$\Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz or } H_2\text{Sal}) = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ} \cdot C \quad (24)$$

where C is the solubility of HBz or H_2 Sal in the appropriate solvent. Equations (22) and (23) thus can be written as

$$\Delta G_{t,Sal}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) + \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\Delta G_{t,neut}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal}) = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal}) + \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal}) + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M} \quad (26)$$

Thus, $\Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ}$ terms can be calculated as all other terms in the above equations are known. It is evident that $[\Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal}) - \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz})]$ represents the $\Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}$ due to H-bonding, i.e. standard Gibbs energy changes due to structural and chemical interactions resulting from the introduction of OH-group in the *ortho*-position of benzoic acid. $\Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{OH})$ (due to hydrogen bonding) are presented in Table 4. The Gibbs energies of transfer of anions can be represented as

$$\Delta G_{t}^{\circ}(\text{Bz}^-) = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{Bz}^-) + \Delta G_{t(e)}^{\circ} + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M} \quad (27)$$

and

$$\Delta G_{t}^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-) = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-) + \Delta G_{t(e)}^{\circ} + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M} \quad (28)$$

From these equations, it is possible to calculate $\Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{Bz}^-)$ and $\Delta G_{t(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HSal}^-)$ with variation of solvent compositions.

The calculation of $\Delta G_{t(e)}^{\circ}(\text{Bz}^- \text{ or } \text{HSal}^-)$ poses a problem. The limitations of Born equation^{1,2} are well known. Even in case of spherical ions like Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- etc., the results are found to be defective. Therefore, the equation will be defective in case of unsymmetrical ions (like benzoate or salicylate ions). Unfortunately, there is no equation which can be utilised unequivocally even in case of spherical ions.

We are forced to use the Born equation assuming spherical orientation of solvent molecules around

TABLE 4—FREE ENERGY (kJ mol^{-1}) OF TRANSFER OF SALICYLIC ACID, BENZOIC ACID AND RELATED TERMS, IN ETHANOL + WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Ethanol wt%	$\Delta G_{t,neut}^{\circ}$		$\Delta G_{t,cav}^{\circ}$ *		$\Delta G_{t,int}^{\circ}$ **		$\Delta G_{t,int}^{\circ}(\text{OH})\dagger$
	HBz	H_2 Sal	HBz	H_2 Sal	HBz	H_2 Sal	
8.0	-0.78	-0.83	0.68	0.41	-1.62	-1.40	0.22
16.4	-1.75	-1.98	1.89	1.26	-3.96	-3.56	0.40
25.3	-3.57	-3.99	5.93	4.10	-10.00	-8.59	1.41
34.4	-6.28	-6.83	21.22	14.97	-28.22	-22.52	5.70
44.0	-8.20	-9.04	47.02	37.23	-56.18	-47.23	8.95
54.1	-9.48	-10.24	78.56	59.64	-89.27	-71.11	18.16
64.7	-10.18	-11.13	101.63	83.56	-113.36	-96.24	17.12
76.0	-10.78	-11.65	124.99	99.16	-137.70	-112.74	24.97
87.6	-11.25	-11.92	145.60	106.58	-159.22	-120.87	38.35

* $\Delta G_{t,cav}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{t(cav)}^{\circ} \cdot C_s$ ** $\Delta G_{t,int}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{t,neut}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{t,cav}^{\circ} - RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_M}$ † $\Delta G_{t,int}^{\circ}(\text{OH}) = \Delta G_{t,int}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) - \Delta G_{t,int}^{\circ}(H_2\text{Sal})$.

the benzoate or salicylate ion. Thus $\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ$ is going from water of relative permittivity ϵ_w to a solvent of relative permittivity ϵ_s can be calculated using Born equation,

$$\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ(\text{Born}) = \frac{NZ^2e^2}{2r_{Bz^-}} \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon_s} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_w} \right] \quad (29)$$

The calculation of solvation energy, however, involves not only the energy of interactions arising from Born charging (B), but also energy of interactions like ion-dipole (i-d), ion-induced-dipole (i-i-d), ion-quadrupole (i-q) charge-transfer and other weak interactions^{20, 25, 26}.

According to Muirhead-Gold and Laidler²⁵, the electrostatic term associated with the different charging processes are strictly Gibbs energy terms. Thus, $\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ$ can be written as

$$\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ = \Delta G_{t(oi)(B)}^\circ + \Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ + \Delta G_{t(i-i-d)}^\circ + \Delta G_{t(i-q)}^\circ \quad (30)$$

However, we have omitted the term due to ion-quadrupole interactions for the non-availability of reliable quadrupole moment data of the solvents. The expressions for the changes in Gibbs energy terms are²⁸

$$\Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ = - \frac{nNZ_1e\mu}{(r_1+r_s)^2} \quad (31)$$

and

$$\Delta G_{t(i-i-d)}^\circ = - \frac{nN\alpha(Z_1e)^2}{2(r_1+r_s)^3} \quad (32)$$

where n , μ , α , r_1 and r_s are solvation number (assumed to be 1 in case of the anion), dipole moment, polarisability, radii of the ion and the solvent respectively. The $\Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{t(i-i-d)}^\circ$ in water and alcohols have been calculated using dipole moments μ and calculated radii values the solvents. The polarisabilities of the solvent molecules have been calculated using the relation,

$$\alpha = \frac{n_D^2 - 1}{n_D^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{\rho} \cdot \frac{3}{4\pi N} \quad (33)$$

taking the refractive index values n_D from the literature²⁷.

The values $\Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{t(i-i-d)}^\circ$ in mixed solvents have been calculated assuming the solute to be distributed in the solvents in the ratio of their mole-fraction X_1 and X_2 . Thus,

$$\Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ = [X_1 \Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ(\text{water}) + X_2 \Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ(\text{org. solv.})] - \Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ(\text{water}) \quad (34)$$

The $\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ$, i.e. $[\Delta G_{t(oi)(B)}^\circ + \Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ + \Delta G_{t(i-i-d)}^\circ]$,

values are given in Table 5. Thus, difference in $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Hsal}^-)$ and $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Bz}^-)$ gives the $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{OH})$ (ion) due to hydrogen bonding in case of charged anions. The $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{OH})$ (ion) can be immediately obtained from the values of $[\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Hsal}^-) - \Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Bz}^-)]$ as the terms $\Delta G_{t(\text{cov})}^\circ$, $\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ$ etc. cancel each other. The variations of $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Bz}^-)$, $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Hsal}^-)$ and $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{OH})$ (ion) with solvent compositions are presented in Table 5. It is, thus, possible to find the effect of introduction of OH group in the *ortho*-position on the structural properties of the solvent mixtures.

The results indicate that with the increase in solubility in the organic solvents, the Gibbs energy change (endothermic) due to cavity formation increases continuously but $\Delta G_{t(\text{cov})}^\circ$ for benzoic acid is much greater compared to that of salicylic acid due to hydrogen bonding which makes the dissolution process of salicylic acid in different solvents less favourable. The interaction terms are negative and favourable but $\Delta \Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ$ for OH group is increasingly positive indicating that OH group in the *ortho*-position of benzoic acid hinders dissolution process.

The $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Bz}^-)$ is usually less favourable compared to that of $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{Hsal}^-)$. This is expected as the salicylate anion is stabilised due to hydrogen bonding leading to the greater dissociation of salicylic acid in solution. The $\Delta \Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{ion})$ due to OH group is seen to be increasingly favourable. Thus, the behaviour of OH group in case of neutral acid and charged anions are exactly opposite.

TABLE 5—FREE ENERGY (kJ mol⁻¹) OF TRANSFER OF SALICYLATE, BENZOATE AND RELATED TERMS IN ETHANOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Ethanol wt%	$\Delta G_{t(A^-)}^\circ$		$\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ$ *	$\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ$ **		$\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ(\text{OH}) = (2) - (1)$
	Bz ⁻	HSal ⁻		Bz ⁻ (1)	HSal ⁻ (2)	
8.0	1.31	0.93	1.09	1.35	1.07	-0.28
16.4	2.07	1.16	2.34	1.91	1.00	-0.91
25.3	2.83	1.05	3.86	2.04	0.26	-1.78
34.4	1.83	-0.43	5.81	0.14	-2.12	-2.26
44.0	3.05	-0.13	8.07	0.47	-2.71	-3.18
54.1	4.20	1.11	10.91	-0.22	-3.31	-3.09
64.7	6.00	1.91	14.49	-0.49	-4.58	-4.09
76.0	6.15	3.06	18.29	-2.30	-5.40	-3.10
87.6	6.33	4.55	25.55	-7.56	-9.34	-1.78

* $\Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ = \Delta G_{t, \text{oi}}^\circ(\text{Born}) + \Delta G_{t(i-d)}^\circ + \Delta G_{t(i-i-d)}^\circ$ ** $\Delta G_{t, \text{int}}^\circ = \Delta G_{t(A^-)}^\circ - \Delta G_{t(\text{cov})}^\circ - \Delta G_{t(oi)}^\circ - RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_m}$

It is true that the method suggested by us has limitations, but no method is perfect and can predict only qualitatively the salient features in solutions. Attempts should be made to refine the calculations and derive maximum useful informations on the various aspects of solution chemistry.

Experimental

Absolute alcohol (B.C.P.W., Calcutta) was treated with sufficient amount of preheated calcium oxide, kept overnight and distilled. It was refluxed with metallic sodium and distilled. The middle fraction was used within 24 h. Triple-distilled water was utilised for preparing the solutions. The mixed solvents were prepared by mixing weighed amount of the solvents. Density was determined using a calibrated pycnometer. The dielectric constants of the mixed solvents were taken from the literature⁸⁸.

Salicylic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was used as such. It was, however, heated to 393 K in an air oven for 1 h and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The perchloric acid (G.R., E. Merck) was estimated in the usual way. Sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, succinic acid, potassium hydrogen phthalate and potassium hydrogen phthalate were of guaranteed quality (E. Merck). Potassium hydrogen salicylate was prepared by exact neutralisation of salicylic acid with one equivalent of KOH solution. KClO₄ (Puriss, Fluka) was crystallised from water, dried and kept in a desiccator.

The saturated solutions of the acid in aquo-ethanolic mixtures were prepared and filtered using Campbell solubility apparatus⁸⁹ as described in our previous communications^{11,12} and the solubility values were determined titrimetrically using phenolphthalein indicator. However, in view of possible error creeping into the results due to the presence of OH group, the solubility values, determined spectrophotometrically from the absorptivity values of the appropriately diluted solution at the isobestic point (300 nm) of the absorption curves of salicylic acid and sodium hydrogen salicylate, were preferred. Molar absorptivity values at 30 nm of the acid were also determined.

The solubilities are reported in Table 1. The solubilities together with pH-values of the saturated solutions of the acid were utilised to determine the dissociation constants of the acid as described earlier^{11,12}.

Accurate values of the dissociation constant of salicylic acid were determined conductometrically. The previously determined *K*-values⁶ may be slightly erroneous in view of the use of extrapolated Δ_0 -values of salicylic acid. Therefore, the re-determination of the dissociation constants were made using Fuoss-Kraus method^{9,10}.

The conductances of salicylic acid at different concentrations (2.9×10^{-5} to 5.0×10^{-4} M) and those

for HClO₄, KClO₄ and KHSal (5.0×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-2} M) in the desired mixed solvents were measured using a Leeds and Northrup 4959 conductivity bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$. A 50-cycle or 1000-cycle signal was employed. A Philips conductance cell was fitted into a double-walled Corning vessel containing the experimental solution. Cell constant (0.761 cm^{-1}) was determined in the way described by Jones and Bradshaw⁴⁰.

The measurements were done at 298.15 ± 0.01 K.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.C.D.) thanks, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing a Research Fellowship, and the other (B.P.D.) thanks Swami Biswanath Nanda Maharaj, Principal, Vivekananda Mission Mahavidyalaya, Haldia.

References

1. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, *Chem. Soc., Spect. Publ.*, 1964, 17.
2. A. GOLDSTEIN, L. ARONOW and S. M. KALMAN, "Principles of Drug Action", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1974, pp. 116, 146-149, 159, 192-194.
3. A. ALBERT, "Selective Toxicity", 6th. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1979, pp. 88, 144, 238, 380, 419, 436, 473.
4. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. C. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
5. U. C. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (NF)*, 1966, 50, 451.
6. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 319.
7. R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH. Theory and Practice", Wiley-Interscience, New York, pp. 276-277.
8. C. W. DAVIES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.
9. R. M. FUOSS and C. KRAUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 55, 476, 2390.
10. R. M. FUOSS and F. ACCASINA, "Electrolytic Conductance", Interscience, New York, 1959.
11. A. PAL, S. K. MAITY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 59, 640.
12. A. PAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1987, 268, 378.
13. R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON in "Chemical Physics in Ionic Solutions", eds. B. E. CONWAY and R. G. BARRADAS, Wiley, New York, 1966, Chap. 12.
14. E. M. SAGER, R. A. ROBINSON and R. G. BATES, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand. (A)*, 1968, 68, 305.
15. G. M. PEARSON and C. M. ROCHESTER, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1975, 71, 1058.
16. A. K. BHATTACHARYYA, D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1986, 265, 372.
17. O. POPOVYCH and A. J. DILL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, 41, 456.
18. O. POPOVYCH and R. P. T. TOMKINS, "Non-aqueous Solution Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1981, pp. 193, Tables 5, 6.
19. M. BORN, *Z. Phys.*, 1920, 1, 45.
20. J. I. KIM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, 82, 191; *Z. Phys. Chem. (NF)*, 1978, 113, 129.
21. O. POPOVYCH in "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", 2nd. ed., eds. I. M. KOLTHOFF and P. J. ELVING, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978, Part I, Vol. 2, Chap. 12.
22. Y. MARCUS, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 53.
23. O. POPOVYCH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, 88, 4167.
24. B. S. KRUMGALZ, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1983, 79, 571; 1985, 81, 247.

25. R. ALEXANDER and A. J. PARKER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 5549.
26. O. POPOVYCH, A. GIBOVSKY and D. H. BERNE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **44**, 817.
27. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1973, **69**, 984; 1976, **72**, 601; 1984, **80**, 2445.
28. D. FRANKS in "Physicochemical Process in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", ed. F. FRANKS, Heinemann Educational Book, London, 1969, pp. 71-90.
29. F. FRANKS and D. J. G. IVES, *Quart. Rev. (London)*, 1966, **20**, 1.
30. R. A. PIEROTTI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 281; *Chem. Rev.*, 1976, **76**, 717.
31. C. TRIENER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, **55**, 632.
32. M. H. ABRAHAM and NASCHZADAH, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 79, 2181.
33. U. SEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 2531; 1980, **102**, 2181.
34. S. P. RUDRA, B. P. CHAKRABORTY, K. K. KUNDU and I. N. BASU MALLICK, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.P.)*, 1986, **150**, 211.
35. J. S. MUIRHEAD-GOULD and K. J. LAIDLER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 944.
36. J. O. M. BOCKRIS and A. K. N. REDDY, "Modern Electrochemistry", Plenum/Rosetta, 1970, Vol. I, Chap. 12.
37. "Organic Solvents. Physical Properties and Methods of Purification", eds. J. A. RIDDICK and W. B. Bunger, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
38. G. AKERLOF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4125.
39. A. N. CAMPBELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 179.
40. G. JONES and B. C. BRADSHAW, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1780.